

to diseases, and the slower the epidemic when it enters the polycyclic phase.

This behavior of the model indicates that it is sensitive to variation in r_s . Future development of the model must consider the effect of time-dependent factors on

variation in r_s so as to reflect variation of environment under which ShB epidemics develop. This suggests that the polycyclic nature of ShB must be considered a key characteristic of the disease for its management, and that measures taken in the course

of a cropping season should prove effective. It also indicates a comparatively high sensitivity of the model to variation in the aggregation parameter, and experiments are necessary for its estimation. ■

Use of CERES-Rice model to assess potential yield

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We conducted a field experiment at RARS, Pilicode ($12^{\circ} 12' N$; $75^{\circ} 10' E$; 2755 mm rainfall, 4.4 h of bright sunshine d^{-1}) to test the CERES-Rice model developed under the IBSNAT Project. Soils were well-drained sandy loam of lateritic origin with pH 5.5. The model was tested for five cropping seasons using different dates of transplanting during 1993 and 1994 kharif and 1992-93, 1993-94, and 1994-95 rabi. Popular varieties Jaya (120-125 d), Jyothi (110-125d), and Triveni (95-105d) were used.

The simulated grain yield through the CERES-Rice model was in good agreement with the observed yield during 1993 kharif while simulated grain yield was higher than that of the observed during 1994 kharif on all transplanting dates (Figs. a and b). Heavy rains during 1994 kharif brought floods. Incidence of gall midge and rice bug was also high at the time, leading to a high percentage of grain chaffing (see table).

The CERES-Rice model during rabi runs for a floodwater management scheme and takes into account bund height as well as floodwater maintained through irrigation at three different early stages of crop growth. The actual rabi crop at the field site was in a totally different condition from that mentioned previously. However, it should be noted that the CERES-Rice model simulated higher grain when run during rabi in all three test varieties on all transplanting dates.

This study reveals that the CERES-Rice model needs validation for rabi while it could very well be used during kharif to assess potential grain yields based on simple daily weather variables. ■

a. Actual and simulated grain yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$) of rice varieties on different dates of transplanting during 1993 kharif.

b. Actual and simulated grain yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$) of rice varieties on different dates of transplanting during 1994 kharif.

Percentage of grain chaffing of three test varieties during 1994 kharif on different dates of transplanting. Kerala, India, 1992-95.

Date of transplanting	Jaya		Jyothi		Triveni	
	Good grains (%)	Chaffing (%)	Good grains (%)	Chaffing (%)	Good grains (%)	Chaffing (%)
8 Jun	68.7	31.3	81.1	18.9	90.3	9.7
15 Jun	82.7	17.3	83.6	16.4	88.7	11.3
22 Jun	75.2	24.8	71.6	28.4	82.8	17.2
29 Jun	67.9	32.1	63.0	37.0	84.0	16.0
6 Jul	58.3	41.7	65.0	35.0	64.2	35.8
Av	70.6	29.4	72.9	27.1	82.0	18.0

Environment

Effect of contour hedgerow on runoff, soil loss, and upland rice production

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Most of the hilly areas in Orissa lose a lot of soil during the wet season. Soil loss and runoff, as affected by different contour hedgerows, were quantified and their effects on upland rice production determined.

The study was conducted at DLAP sites in Bhawanipatna in 1993 and in Phulbani in 1994. Soil at both sites is sandy loam with about 2% slope.

Rice (variety 9991 in 1993 and Heera in 1994) was dry-seeded in rows with 20-cm spacing along contours. Hedgerows separated rice terraces. The treatments (9 in 1993 and 7 in 1994) arranged in randomized complete block with three replications were the vegetation used to form the hedgerows (see table).

The hedgerows were planted with 1-yr-old grass seedlings (except for stylo where seeds were sown) 1 mo before the experiment. The distance between two hedgerows was 8 m. Plots were 25 m \times 3 m. Lengthwise, each plot comprised three terraces separated by two hedgerows.

Daily runoff was monitored using a multislit divisor. Runoff collected by one slot is fed into a drum installed at the end of the divisor. A sample of 250 ml was taken from each drum after thorough stirring and